

Hemidesterpene, a new triterpenoid from *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br. root

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Abstract : Chemical investigation of *Hemidesmus indicus* roots yielded α -amyrin acetate, β -amyrin acetate, taraxesteryl acetate and a new triterpenoid designated hemidesterpene. The latter was characterised as $\Delta^{12,13}$ -taraxesteryl acetate from spectroscopical investigations.

Keywords : Anantamul, *Hemidesmus indicus*, triterpenoids, hemidesterpene, $\Delta^{12,13}$ -taraxesteryl acetate.

Introduction

Hemidesmus indicus R.Br.¹⁻⁴ (Indian *Sarsapilla*, *Anantamul* in Bengali and Hindi; *Sariva* in Sanskrit; *Nannari* in Tamil) is a well-known medicinal plant in Ayurveda, the traditional school of Indian medicine. The plant grows widespread all over India. The root-bark and root find use in over 46 drug formulations in the Indian Ayurvedic system of medicine^{3,4}.

Some chemical investigations of the plant have been reported. The constituents reported¹⁻⁶ includes pregnane glycosides, terpenoids, flavone glycosides and coumarinolignoids^{5,6}. The present paper reports further chemical investigations on this plant.

Results and discussion

Roots of *Hemidesmus indicus* were obtained from suppliers in Kolkata. The shade-dried roots (1.5 kg) were crushed and extracted with ethanol at ambient temperature. The extract was concentrated in a Büchi rotary evaporator. The resulting concentrate was extracted with chloroform and then with water for extracting amino-acids, peptides and glycosides. The chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel (Merck) adsorbent with eluents of increasing polarity. The three coumarinolignoids^{5,6}, viz. hemidesminin, hemidesmin-1 and hemidesmin-2 were obtained in the 10% methanolic-ethyl acetate eluates, separated by PTLC and identified by comparison with authentic samples. The 20% chloroform in

petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) eluates yielded a mixture of α -amyrin acetate (1), β -amyrin acetate (2), taraxesteryl acetate (3) and triterpenoid (4). The four triterpenoids were separated by re-chromatography followed by PTLC over silica gel G with petroleum ether-chloroform (1 : 4) as the developing system. α -Amyrin acetate (1)^{7a,8a,9}, β -amyrin acetate (2)^{7b,8b,9} and taraxesteryl acetate (3)^{7c,8c,10,11} were characterised by ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra and by direct comparison with authentic samples.

The fourth triterpenoid, designated as hemidesterpene, was obtained as an amorphous white powder, m.p. 182–184 °C, $[\alpha]_D^{+25}$ (CHCl₃). It exhibited a molecular ion peak at M⁺ 466 corresponding to C₃₂H₅₀O₂. Hemidesterpene was assigned structure $\Delta^{12,13}$ -taraxesteryl acetate (4) from spectroscopical investigations.

Its IR spectrum showed bands for an acetoxy group (1670, 1250 cm⁻¹) and an exocyclic methylene (970 cm⁻¹). Its 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum showed the presence of an acetoxy group (δ 2.03), a vinylic proton triplet (δ 5.18, *J* 3.5 Hz), six tertiary and one secondary methyl groups. The H-3 proton appeared as a double doublet at δ 4.38, its coupling constants (*J* 9.0, 5.4 Hz) confirming its α -axial orientation. ¹H, ¹H-COSY and ¹H-decoupling experiments established the following relationships : H-11 methylene (δ 1.90–1.95) - H-12 (δ 5.18); and H-18 (δ 1.68) - H-19 multiplet (δ 2.42) - C-29 (d, δ 1.12). Two mutually coupled protons at δ 4.69 and δ 4.57 (*J* 2.4 Hz)

showed the presence of an exocyclic methylene group.

Its EI-MS exhibited a fragmentation pattern similar to α -amyrin acetate indicating that it belonged to the same ursane skeletal pattern. Fragments at m/z 249 and m/z 216 corresponded to the retro-Diels Alder fragmentation of ring C with cleavage at 9//14 and 8//11 bonds. Further peaks appeared at m/z 465 ($M^+ - H$), 450 (465-Me), 406 (M-HOAc), 201 (216-Me), 189 (249-HOAc), 174 (189-Me), 43 (CH_3CO , base peak). Comparison of the 300 MHz 1H NMR and 75.5 MHz ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts (Table 1) of hemidesterpene (**4**) with those of α -amyrin acetate (**1**)^{7a,8a,9}, β -amyrin acetate (**2**)^{7b,8b,9} and taraxesteryl acetate (**3**)^{7c,8c,10,11} helped in its structure elucidation. The ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts of hemidesterpene (**4**) were nearly identical for rings A, B and C with α -amyrin acetate (**1**) and only for rings A and B of β -amyrin acetate (**2**) establishing thereby that (**4**) belonged to the ursane rather than oleanane skeleton. The ^{13}C NMR of chemical shifts of rings D and E carbons of hemidesterpene (**4**) were similar with those of taraxesteryl acetate (**3**), indicating the presence of $\Delta^{20,30}$ -exocyclic double bond with a similar stereochemistry of rings D and E.

Thus the complete structure and stereochemistry of hemidesterpene stands clarified as $\Delta^{12,13}$ -dehydro-taraxesteryl acetate (**4**).

Literature search showed a publication from *Calotropis gigantea* by Ali *et al.*¹²; this reported the isolation and characterisation of gigantesuryl acetate as urs-18 β -H-12(30) dien-3 β -yl acetate. However, the structure was represented as urs-18 α -H-12,20(30) dien-3 β -yl acetate. Later, this latter formulation was named procerausenyl acetate – this was isolated from *Calotropis procera* (AIT) R.Br¹³. Inconsistencies in the 1H NMR with these structure were their assignments of H-3 α at δ 3.40 and H-18 at δ 2.81. These signals are not consistent with either structural formulation. The NMR data given for either of these compounds are different in several respects from hemidesterpene (**4**), which is diastereoisomeric with these two formulations.

Experimental

General :

Instruments : Bruker AV-300 NMR spectrometer (300

Table 1. 75.5 MHz ^{13}C NMR assignments in $CDCl_3$

Carbon no.	Multiplicity	Chemical shifts in ppm			
		1	2	3	4
1	t	38.54	38.54	38.40	38.64
2	t	23.60	23.60	23.60	23.70
3	d	80.95	80.95	80.80	81.04
4	s	37.71	37.71	37.70	37.81
5	d	55.35	55.35	55.40	55.45
6	t	18.26	18.26	18.10	18.36
7	t	32.93	32.67	33.90	32.77
8	s	40.11	39.66	40.80	40.08
9	d	47.60	47.70	50.30	47.72
10	s	36.80	36.80	37.00	36.94
11	t	23.20	23.37	21.40	23.46
12	d	124.37	121.68	25.50	124.47
13	s	139.64	144.00	38.80	139.73
14	s	42.10	42.15	41.90	42.25
15	t	28.67	28.67	26.60	26.74
16	t	26.64	26.17	39.10	38.30
17	s	33.72	33.72	34.40	33.81
18	d	59.18	47.30	48.60	48.50
19	d	39.66	46.85	39.30	40.21
20	s	39.62	31.10	154.40	152.00
21	t	31.23	34.70	25.40	28.23
22	t	41.54	37.17	38.30	38.64
23	q	28.13	28.13	27.80	28.14
24	q	16.80	16.80	16.40	16.74
25	q	15.60	15.60	15.40	15.73
26	q	16.40	16.64	16.20	16.97
27	q	23.20	25.88	14.60	14.58
28	q	28.13	29.01	19.40	17.48
29	t	17.40	32.20	26.10	28.14
30	t	21.08	21.25	107.00	109.33
OCOCH ₃	s	21.25	21.08	21.10	21.17
OCO	s	170.72	170.72	170.80	170.79

MHz H-1, 75.5 MHz C-13, $CDCl_3$ solvent), Perkin-Elmer FT-IR RX-9 spectrometer.

Plant material : Roots of *Hemidesmus indicus* was purchased in Kolkata from traditional material drug suppliers and identified at NRIADD Botany Department.

Extraction and isolation : Shade-dried powdered roots of *H. indicus* (1.5 kg) was extracted with ethanol (95%) at ambient temperature. The extract (2.5 lit.) was concentrated in a Büchi rotary evaporator. The resulting concentrate was extracted with chloroform and then with

(1) α -Amyrin acetate

(2) β -Amyrin acetate

(3) Taraxesteryl acetate

(4) Hemidesterpene

(4) Hemidesterpene

water for extracting amino-acids, peptides and glycosides. The chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel adsorbent (Merck, 60–100 mesh) with eluents of increasing polarity. Three coumarino-lignoids, viz. hemidesminin, hemidesmin-1 and hemidesmin-2 were obtained in the 10% methanolic-ethyl acetate eluates. These were separated by PTLC over silica-gel G (Merck) and were identified by comparison with authentic samples. A

mixture of triterpenoids was obtained in the 20% chloroform in petroleum ether (60–80 °C). The four triterpenoids were separated by re-chromatography followed by PTLC over silica gel (Merck) with petroleum ether-chloroform (1 : 4) as the developing system. α -Amyrin acetate (66 mg), m.p. 224–225 °C, β -amyrin acetate (34 mg), m.p. 242–243 °C and taraxesteryl acetate (24 mg), m.p. 253–254 °C were identified from their ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data^{7–11}

and comparison with authentic samples. A fourth triterpenoid designated hemidesterpene (**4**), amorphous white powder, m.p. 182–184 °C (44 mg) was also obtained.

Hemidesterpene (4) - Δ^{12,13}-taraxesteryl acetate : m.p. 182–184 °C, amorphous white powder, $[\alpha]_D^{+82}$ (CHCl₃); IR ν_{\max} , (KBr) : 2940, 2855, 1735, 1670, 1250, 970, 810 cm⁻¹; 300 MHz ¹H NMR, δ (CDCl₃) : 1.02, 0.96, 0.94, 0.92, 0.89, 0.83 (3H, s each; six methyls – 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28), 1.12 (d, *J* 5.6 Hz, CH₃-29), 2.03 (-COCH₃), 4.38 (dd, *J* 9.0, 5.7 Hz, H-3), 4.57 and 4.69 (1H, d each, *J* 2.4 Hz, H-30), 5.18 (t, *J* 3.5 Hz, H-12), 1.68 (m, H-18), 1.90–1.95 (2H, m, H-11), 2.42 (1H, multiplet, H-19), 2.10–2.24 (2H, m, H-21), other proton signals appeared as overlapped ill-resolved multiplets in the region δ 1.10 to δ 1.97. MS : 70 eV EI-MS : *m/z* 466 (M⁺), 465 (M⁺-H), *m/z* 450 (465-Me), 406 (M-HOAc), 249 and 216 corresponding to the retro-Diels Alder fragmentation of ring C with cleavage at 9//14 and 8//11, 201 (216-Me), 189 (249-HOAc), 174 (189-Me), 43 (CH₃CO, 100%).

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